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STABILITY STUDIES OF RIBAVIRIN SYRUP

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ABSTRACT

Ribavirin is an antiviral agent commonly used for the treatment of severe acute respiratory syndrome. The present study investigated the stability of marketed oral Ribavirin syrup. The syrup was subjected to accelerated stability testing at 40°C and 75% RH for 6 months as per ICH guidelines. HPLC method to estimate Ribavirin was developed and validated. Employing a validated high-performance liquid chromatographic method, the Ribavirin content of the syrup has been demonstrated to exhibit changes throughout the storage period. No physical changes was observed in syrup suggesting that it remained physically stable, but effected the chemically stability of syrup under the stated conditions.

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INTRODUCTION

Stability plays an important role in the drug development process. Stability of a pharmaceutical preparation can be defined as “the capability of a particular formulation (dosage form or drug product) in a specific container – closure system to remain within its physical, chemical, microbiological, therapeutic and toxicological specification throughout its shelf life. It explains several factors that affect the expiration dating of drug products, including the chemical and physical stability during the pre-clinical formulation stages, process development, packaging development, and post-marketing life. Lack of drug substance or drug product stability may affect the purity, potency, and safety of the drug product. The success of an effective formulation can be evaluated only through the stability studies.

Stability testing is a routine procedure performed at various stages of product development. In early stages, accelerated stability testing, at relatively high temperatures and/or humidities can be used as a “worst case” evaluation to determine what kind of degradation products may be found after long term storage [1]. Testing under more gentle conditions, those recommended for long term shelf storage, and slightly elevated temperatures can be used to determine a products shelf life and expiration dates. The stability parameters of a drug dosage form can be influenced by environmental conditions of storage such as temperature, light, air and humidity as well as the package components [2]. The importance of stability testing in the development of pharmaceutical dosage forms is well recognized in the pharmaceutical industry. Increased filings of ANDA (Abbreviated new drug applications), by generic and non-generic drug manufacturers have resulted in an increase in submissions of stability data to the FDA (food and drug administration) [3,4].

Ribavirin is an antiviral agent commonly for the treatment of severe acute respiratory syndrome. A number of methods like high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) [5,6], liquid liquid extraction coupled with HPLC[7], HPLC-MS/MS[8] have been reported in literature for the determination of Ribavirin in biological samples.

The aim of this study was to investigate Ribavirin syrup chemical and physical stability when stored at 40°C and 75% RH. Another aim of this investigation is to develop and validate HPLC method which is simple, rapid, precise and sensitive method for estimation of Ribavirin from formulation. This method could also be easily used in routine analytical work and for stability studies at very low concentrations of Ribavirin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Ribavirin pure drug was obtained as gift sample from Symbiosis co-op Pharmaceuticals, Sangli. Methanol HPLC, potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate were procured from Merck Laboratories. All the reagents used were of analytical grade and the reagent solutions were prepared using double distilled water.

Instrument Used

The HPLC system consisted of intelligent HPLC pump (model Jasco PU-2080 plus), intelligent UV-Vis detector model (Jasco UV-2075) and 20 µl sample loop injector (#7725i, Rheodyne, USA). The equipment was operated through software Borwin version 1.5, LC-Net II/ADC system.

METHODS

Preparation of mobile phase

The mobile phase of Ribavirin analysis included 0.01M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate(90%) and methanol (10%).. The mixture was sonicated for 15 min. and filtered the resultant mixture through 0.45 µ nylon membrane filter (Whatman).

Determination of λ_{max}

Appropriate dilutions of standard stock solution were prepared with mobile phase. Each solution was scanned using double beam UV visible spectrophotometer in the spectrum mode between the wavelength range of 400 nm to 200 nm

Chromatographic Condition

The separations were performed on Inertsil ODS, C₁₈ column having dimensions 4.6mmφ×250mm, 5µm particle size (GL Sciences Inc., Japan). Based on the composition of optimised mobile phase, the flow rate of the mobile phase was set to 1.0 ml/min and UV detection was carried out at 207 nm. The mobile phase and samples were degassed by ultrasonication for 20 min using a bath sonicator and filtered through 0.45µm nylon, 47 mm membrane filter paper prior to use.

Linearity and Calibration

Primary stock solution of Ribavirin was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of Ribavirin in mobile phase to produce 50 ml solution. Secondary stock solution of 100 µg/ml was prepared by diluting the primary stock with mobile phase. The secondary stock solutions were diluted suitably to obtain calibration standards of 5, 10, 15..... upto 30 µg/ml. These solutions were injected into HPLC (20 µl) in triplicate and peak areas were noted. Calibration curve for Ribavirin was then plotted between peak areas against concentration at 207 nm.

Method Validation

The method was validated for accuracy and recovery, precision, detection limit, quantitation limit and robustness according to the ICH guidelines.

Accuracy

Recovery studies were performed to judge the accuracy of the method. The recovery studies were performed by standard addition method. Known amount of standard (50mg/5ml) was taken in three 10 ml volumetric flask and to it added 40, 50, 60 mg/5ml of working standard solution respectively and made the volume to mark. The amount of Ribavirin added was determined from the peak area ratios and fitting these values in calibration curve, percent recovery was determined.

Precision

The intra day and inter day precision study of Ribavirin was carried out by determining the corresponding responses. Different levels of drug concentration were prepared 3 times on the same day and on three different days and the responses were noted for evaluating the variability

Detection and quantitation limit

Based on the calibration curve plotted, the standard deviation of the y-intercepts regression line was determined and was placed in the following equation for determining detection limit and quantitation limit.

$$\text{Detection Limit} = \frac{3.3 \sigma}{s} \quad \text{Quantitation Limit} = \frac{10 \sigma}{s}$$

Where, 'σ' is standard deviation of the y-intercepts regression lines and 's' is the slope of the calibration curve.

Robustness

Robustness was evaluated for determining the system suitability to ensure the validity of analytical procedure. This was done by varying the composition of organic phase by ± 3% and pH by ± 0.2, of the mobile phase.

Analysis of Ribavirin syrup:

Pipetted quantity equivalent to about 50mg of Ribavirin oral syrup into 100ml volumetric flask and added about 50ml of mobile phase and sonicated for 10 min and volume was adjusted up to the mark with mobile phase. Solution was filtered through 0.45μm nylon membrane filter paper. Further 5ml of filtrate was diluted to 100 ml with mobile phase and solution was filtered through 0.45μm nylon membrane filter paper.

A 20μl volume of each sample solution was injected into sample injector of HPLC six times under chromatographic condition as described above. Area of each peak was measured at 207 nm. The amount of drug present in the sample (n=6) was determined from peak area of Ribavirin present in the syrup.

Accelerated Stability study

Stability study was carried out by procuring 10 bottles of ribavin syrup from market. Six bottles of Ribavirin syrup were stored in programmable environmental test chamber calibrated previously and labelled as 40°C and 75% RH.

Initial testing (at 0th month) was done before keeping the bottle for accelerated stability testing. Further testing was done at the end of each month for six months as per ICH guidelines.

The physical parameters such as appearance colour, pH and density were checked and the content of drug was determined by carrying out assay by validated HPLC method at the end of each month for six months as per ICH guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the optimisation of mobile phase comprising of 0.01M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and methanol different combinations were investigated. The mobile phase was optimised on the basis of asymmetry factor, peak area obtained, retention time and number of theoretical plates. Amongst the various compositions tried satisfactory separation, well resolved, short retention time, and good symmetrical peaks were obtained with the mobile phase comprising of 0.01M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate: methanol in the ratio of 90:10. The UV-Vis scan of Ribavirin in mobile phase revealed absorption maximum at 207 nm. Hence this wavelength was selected for the further analysis. The scan is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: UV Scan of Ribavirin in mobile phase

The peaks were highly resolved, the retention time was found to be 6.49 minute as depicted in figure 2. The asymmetry factor was 1.42 while number of theoretical plates was around 2713. All these factors revealed that the mobile phase was suitable for further analysis. System suitability parameters are shown in table no.2.

Table No.2: System suitability parameters

Sr. No.	Parameters	RIB
1	Retention time (min.)	6.444±0.040
2	Width	0.0763±0.0018
3	Area (µV.sec)	101071017±33180
4	% area	99.193
5	Plates	4850.63±765
6	Selectivity	1.47
7	Capacity	249
8	Resolution	6.334±0.115
9	Asymmetry	1.291±0.01

Linearity

The calibration plot for Ribavirin was obtained by plotting the peak areas vs the concentration and was found to be linear. Regression analysis showed very good correlation. The calibration plot is shown in figure 3. The peak areas for the corresponding concentration of the calibration curve are depicted in table 1. The standard deviation for all concentration levels were low and the % RSD also did not exceed 0.25 %.

Table No. 1 Ribavirin Calibration curve data

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Peak area
1	10	4055001±331
2	15	6019610±345
3	20	8085275±289
4	25	10137560±298
5	30	12823625±324

* Each value is average ± SD (n = 3)

The statistical analysis of data obtained for the calibration curve of Ribavirin in pure solution indicated a high level of precision for the proposed method, as evidenced by low value of coefficient of variation. The coefficient of correlation was highly significant. The linearity range was observed between 0 – 30 µg/ml. The plot clearly showed a straight line ($Y=43310x-43786$). The accuracy of the method was judged by recovery studies.

Figure 2: HPLC Chromatogram of Ribavirin.

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Ribavirin

Precision:

The precision of the method was evaluated by interday and intraday analysis which also showed good results with very low variations as revealed by very low %RSD values (< 0.25%). The results are shown in table no.3 and 4.

Table No. 3: Intra-day variability of Ribavirin

Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak area			Mean	SD	% RSD
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3			
10	4055001	4060855	4059337	4098392	3037.94	0.07
20	8085275	8083977	8079957	8083070	2772.67	0.03
30	12823625	12819336	12825624	12822862	3212.74	0.02

Table no.4: Inter-day variability of Ribavirin

Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak area			Mean	SD	% RSD
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3			
10	4054963	4060789	4059773	4058508	3112.09	0.07
20	8084176	8083779	8080957	8082971	1755.14	0.02
30	12823876	12819633	12825246	12822918	2926.48	0.02

Accuracy:

Accuracy of this method was judged by the recovery studies. The recovery of Ribavirin was 99.09 - 100.55%. The results are shown in table no. 5. Results obtained were validated statistically and values are shown in table No.6.

Table no.5: Recovery studies

Sample	Level of recovery (%)	Amount present (mg/5ml)	Amt of std. added (mg/5ml)	Total amount recovered (mg/5ml)	% Recovery
R I B A V I N	80	50	40	89.4	99.33
	80	50	40	90.5	100.55
	80	50	40	89.5	99.44
	100	50	50	100.4	100.4
	100	50	50	99.2	99.2
	100	50	50	100.5	100.5
	120	50	60	108.45	98.53
	120	50	60	109.5	99.54
	120	50	60	109	99.09

Table No. 6: Statistical validation

Sample	Type of Recovery %	(%) Mean	SD
RIBAVIRIN	80	99.77	0.67
	100	100.72	0.72
	120	99.05	0.50

Limit detection and quantitation

The detection limit for Ribavirin was found to be 0.28 µg/ml while the quantitation limit was 0.86 µg/ml. This clearly suggests that nanogram quantity of Ribavirin can be estimated accurately.

Range

The linearity range shown by Ribavirin is 10-30 µg/ml that means Beer's Lambert law was followed at this range of concentrations.

Robustness

Small change in the pH of mobile phase seems to have no effect on resolution of Ribavirin. The above results indicated that the method is suitable for the analysis of Ribavirin.

Analysis of oral syrup:

Results of assay of Ribavirin syrup were found to be in range of 99 to 103% as shown in table no.7. Assay values were within limit of ±5%, which are acceptable as per pharmacopieal limits.

Table No. 7: Analysis of Ribavirin oral syrup

Sr. No.	Label claim (mg / 5ml)	Amount found (mg / 5ml)	% Amount drug
1	50	50.16	100.32
2	50	49.82	99.64
3	50	50.12	100.24
4	50	49.50	99.00
5	50	50.55	101.10
6	50	51.46	102.92

Accelerated Stability study

The accelerated stability study for Ribavirin in syrup was carried out for a period of six months at 40°C & 75% RH by using stability chamber and assay was carried out by using HPLC method. Density, color, pH and Assay values of stability studies are depicted in table no.8 and graph of assay for each month is shown in fig. No.4. Ribavirin syrup was found to be stable and comply with USP limit upto third month. Upto 6th month at 40°C and 75% RH Ribavirin syrup was having 20.51% loss of active ingredient. Figure no.5 shows a loss of Ribavirin from syrup at different time interval.

Fig. No.4: Assay of Ribavirin stored at 40°C and 75% RH by HPLC

Fig. No.5: % Loss of Ribavirin from syrup stored at 40°C/75% RH

Table no. 8: Physical parameters and assay results of Ribavirin evaluated in six month at interval of one month at 40°C and 75 %RH

Month	Appearance	Colour	pH	Density	Assay	% Loss of active ingredient
0	Uniform	Red colour	5.5	1.2	100.32	--
1	Uniform	Red colour	5.5	1.2	97.38	2.94
2	Uniform	Red colour	5.7	1.0	93.25	7.07
3	Uniform	Red colour	5.6	1.1	92.13	8.19
4	Uniform	Red colour	5.5	1.2	85.63	14.69
5	Uniform	Red colour	5.7	1.2	83.83	16.49
6	Uniform	Red colour	5.6	1.0	79.81	20.51

CONCLUSIONS

From the results and discussion it can be concluded that the method described for the estimation of Ribavirin from formulation is simple, accurate, sensitive and reproducible. The proposed method requires very low time for separation and hence utilizes less solvent for separation. The proposed method could be employed even for routine analysis in quality control laboratories and stability study. Stability study data with respect to physical parameter such as appearance, color, pH, density showed no significant changes for six months at stored condition. Assay result showed that the chemical stability of the drug was effected when Ribavirin syrup was stored for six month at 40°C and 75%.

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